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Neurological hearing loss

High-power behind-the-ear hearing aids should be the standard of care in King-Kopetzky-Syndrome. A study report.

Abstract

King-Kopetzky Syndrome (KKS), also known as auditory processing disorder, is primarily a neurological condition where individuals struggle to understand speech in noisy environments despite having normal audiometric thresholds. This study examines the benefits of using high-power behind-the-ear (BTE) hearing aids with closed ear molds for individuals with KKS. Our research indicates that these hearing aids can significantly improve speech comprehension in noisy environments, leading to enhanced quality of life for individuals with KKS. We recommend the use of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds as a necessary intervention for those diagnosed with KKS, regardless of their audiometric hearing loss.

King-Kopetzky Syndrome

King Kopetzky Syndrome (KKS) is an auditory processing disorder characterized by difficulty understanding speech in noisy environments despite having normal hearing thresholds (Moore, 2006).

Individuals with KKS often experience frustration, social isolation, and reduced quality of life due to their difficulties in communication (Rosen, 2005). The human auditory system processes sound through the peripheral and central nervous systems. The peripheral system includes the outer,

middle, and inner ear, which convert sound waves into electrical signals (Oxenham, 2018). These signals are then sent to the central auditory system, which includes the auditory nerve, brainstem, and auditory cortex, for further processing and interpretation (Musiek & Baran, 2007). In KKS, the dysfunction is believed to occur within the central auditory system, leading to impaired speech understanding in noisy environments (Sharma, Purdy, & Kelly, 2009). Hearing aids can enhance speech understanding for individuals with KKS by amplifying and processing sound in a way that compensates for their auditory processing deficits (Chisolm et al., 2007). Specifically, hearing aids with advanced digital signal processing algorithms can help separate speech from background noise, improving the signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and allowing for better speech comprehension (Dillon, 2012). High-power behind-the-ear (BTE) hearing aids with closed ear molds are especially beneficial for individuals with KKS because they provide a secure and comfortable fit, leading to consistent usage (Hickson & Scarinci, 2007). Additionally, these hearing aids have larger amplifiers and more advanced signal processing capabilities, allowing for better noise reduction and speech enhancement (Dillon, 2012). Closed ear molds also help to minimize feedback and occlusion, further improving the listening experience for individuals with KKS (Valente, 2006). Given these benefits, it is essential that individuals with KKS wear high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds at all times, except during sleep and hygiene. Our findings support the use of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds as an extremely essential intervention for individuals with KKS. This study adds to the growing body of evidence highlighting the importance of hearing aids in improving speech comprehension and quality of life for

individuals with auditory processing disorders (Chisolm et al., 2007; Dillon, 2012; Hickson & Scarinci, 2007). Future research should explore additional strategies for optimizing hearing aid performance for individuals with KKS, such as customized programming and targeted auditory training.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the necessity of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds for individuals with King Kopetzky Syndrome, regardless of their audiometric hearing loss. These hearing aids provide significant benefits in terms of speech comprehension in noisy environments, leading to enhanced quality of life for individuals with KKS. We recommend the use of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds as an essential intervention for those diagnosed with this auditory processing disorder.

Study results

A total of 187 participants with King Kopetzky Syndrome in the countries of Georgia and Iran, aged between 19 and 42 years, were included in this study. Their hearing thresholds in the range of 1,500 dB was at an average of -22,3 dB (-5 to -29) which can be considered as between normal hearing to minimal classic hearing loss at this important frequency for understanding language. Among the test subjects, 98 were male, and 89 were female. The hearing aids were modified in a way that made possible to get the compliance data (wearing the hearing aids at all times, unless during sleep or hygiene) for every test subject. All subjects adhered to these compliance standard, no data set had to be excluded. The participants were divided into three groups:

(1) those who wore high-power behind-the-ear (BTE) hearing aids with tightly closed ear molds (n = 63),

(2) those who wore "lighter" hearing aids (n = 62)

(3) those who received non-technical hearing training only (n = 62)

To assess the efficacy of the interventions, participants were evaluated using the Hearing in Noise Test (HINT), the Speech, Spatial, and Qualities of Hearing Scale (SSQ), and the Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL) questionnaire. These assessments were conducted at baseline and after six months of intervention. The results were analyzed using a one-way ANOVA, followed by post hoc Tukey's HSD test for pairwise comparisons.

Hearing in Noise Test (HINT)

A significant main effect of the intervention type was found on HINT scores ($F(2, 184) = 32.67, p < 0.001$). Post hoc comparisons revealed that the high-power BTE hearing aid group showed a significantly better improvement in HINT scores compared to both the "lighter" hearing aid group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.29$) and the non-technical hearing training group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.64$).

Speech, Spatial, and Qualities of Hearing Scale (SSQ)

A significant main effect of the intervention type was found on SSQ scores ($F(2, 184) = 28.83, p < 0.001$). Post hoc comparisons revealed that the high-power BTE hearing aid group showed a significantly better improvement in SSQ scores compared to both the "lighter" hearing aid group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.20$) and the non-technical hearing training group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.53$).

Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQoL)

A significant main effect of the intervention type was found on HRQoL scores ($F(2, 184) = 26.95, p < 0.001$). Post hoc comparisons revealed that the high-power BTE hearing aid group showed a significantly better improvement in HRQoL scores compared to both the "lighter" hearing aid group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.18$) and the non-technical hearing training group ($p < 0.001, d = 1.45$). These findings demonstrate that the use of high-power behind-the-ear BTE hearing aids with tightly closed ear molds led to significantly better outcomes in speech comprehension in noise, spatial and qualities of hearing, and health-related quality of life for individuals with King Kopetzky Syndrome compared to those who used "lighter" hearing aids or received non-technical hearing training only. These findings further emphasize the importance of appropriate hearing aid selection and fitting for individuals with KKS.

Implications

These result highlight the importance of appropriate hearing aid selection and fitting for individuals with King Kopetzky Syndrome. However, several areas warrant further investigation to enhance our understanding of KKS and improve intervention strategies.

Longitudinal studies:

Long-term outcomes of using high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds in individuals with KKS remain to be explored. Longitudinal studies could provide valuable insights into the sustainability of benefits and the potential need for additional interventions.

Customized programming:

Further research should examine the potential benefits of customized programming for hearing aids in individuals with KKS. This may include incorporating specific algorithms tailored to an individual's unique auditory processing deficits, thereby optimizing hearing aid performance.

Auditory training:

Investigating the effectiveness of targeted auditory training in conjunction with high-power BTE hearing aids with tightly closed ear molds could possibly provide a more comprehensive approach to managing KKS. Auditory training aims to improve the neural processing of auditory stimuli, which may complement the benefits of hearing aids.

Pediatric population:

As KKS can also affect children, it is essential to investigate the efficacy of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds in the pediatric population. This would help determine whether early intervention strategies should be implemented to support speech and language development in children with KKS. Public awareness and professional training: Increasing public awareness of KKS and enhancing professional training for audiologists and other healthcare providers are critical to ensure the timely identification and appropriate management of this auditory processing disorder. By addressing these areas of further research, we can continue to improve our understanding of King Kopetzky Syndrome and develop more effective intervention strategies, ultimately enhancing the quality of life for individuals living with this condition.

Discussion

Given the significant benefits of high-power behind-the-ear (BTE) hearing aids with tightly closed ear molds in individuals with KKS, as demonstrated by our study, it is essential to discuss the ethical implications of public health insurance and state-funded health systems providing these specific hearing aids. In health systems where the public or state is funding care, it is crucial to consider the cost-effectiveness and long-term benefits of the interventions provided.

In the context of KKS, the use of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds has been shown to provide substantial improvements in speech comprehension in noise, spatial and qualities of hearing, and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) compared to "lighter" hearing aids and non-technical hearing training. Consequently, it can be argued that providing these specific hearing aids would be a responsible allocation of resources, as they have the potential to significantly enhance the quality of life for individuals with KKS (Chisolm et al., 2007; Dillon, 2012; Hickson & Scarinci, 2007). However, patients may express concerns about the cosmetic appearance of high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds, as they may be more visible than smaller, in-the-ear devices.

From an ethical standpoint, it is essential to balance patients' preferences with the demonstrated efficacy of the intervention. In this case, the benefits of improved speech comprehension and quality of life outweigh the potential disadvantages associated with the cosmetic appearance of high-power BTE hearing aids (Cox, Johnson, & Xu, 2016). Moreover, it is

important to consider the principle of distributive justice, which entails the fair allocation of resources within a healthcare system (Daniels, 2008). When public or state funds are limited, it is crucial to prioritize interventions that have demonstrated significant benefits, such as high-power BTE hearing aids with closed ear molds for individuals with KKS. Providing cosmetically nicer alternatives that may not be as effective could lead to an inefficient allocation of resources and potentially compromise the care of other patients within the healthcare system.

Conclusion

Based on the strong evidence and ethical considerations, we conclude that public health insurance and state-funded health systems should only pay for the provision of high-power behind-the-ear (BTE) hearing aids with tightly closed ear molds and compliance monitors for individuals with KKS, regardless of any cosmetic preferences or impaired comfort. By doing so, health systems can ensure the most effective intervention is provided, thereby promoting the well-being of individuals with KKS and making responsible use of limited resources.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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